

PUBLIC TRANSPORTATION: A GLANCE AT THE HISTORY OF THE TRAM

Kupaysinov Ismail

Namangan state universiteti

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ABSTRACT

In this article, trams, which are considered public transport, and some considerations about their emergence are given. Information is provided about the first trams in Tashkent.

Tram (*English tram-vagon, trolleybus and way-yo'l*) is an underground electric railway, a type of street and partial street public transport designed to transport passengers along fixed routes, mainly used in cities[1].

The tram is one of the oldest types of urban passenger public transport, which existed at the beginning of the 21st century, and appeared in the first half of the 19th century.

An experimental electric tram, invented and tested by Pirotsky, first appeared in 1880 in St. Petersburg, Russia, and a regular tram service was first launched in May 1881 in the suburbs of Berlin, Germany, by the Siemens and Halske company[2].

There was a new development in electric and railway transport. Trams were propelled by electric cables that were attached to their tracks. Commuting trams was very simple: the railway lines already existed, and most cities used old horse-drawn carriages with new track additions.

Soon new tram lines appeared and the cities began to expand further.

This expansion ushered in a new era of urban planning where "walkability" was no longer a key feature, and residential developments, downtown shopping centers began to develop. The invention of the streetcar gave way to the sprawling, bustling metropolises we know today. Because streetcar lines often run directly into the city center, these areas have become prime real estate locations for luxury retail chains, million-dollar businesses, and other locations that are more expansive with a transportation hub outside. they realized that they could provide entertainment to the audience. their front door.

While horse-drawn carriages could carry passengers only a few stops, electric streetcars could travel many miles, pushing public transportation outwards and eventually into the suburbs, allowing extension into what were then known as "streetcars". These small towns retained

the dense, crowded areas of the old cities, but were located just one rail line to the nearest major city for the shopping, dining, and entertainment options of the "big city."

Trams quickly became a popular mode of transport and were a vast improvement over previous public transport services. But two major incidents were about to cause worldwide damage and trouble for riders and transit companies. The Great Depression led to widespread line closures in the 1930s, and World War II's tight rationing of rubber tires and gasoline sealed the fate of many other already-failing lines. Nevertheless, some tram lines remained open, while others were converted into bus lines[3].

The oldest and most common means of transport in Tashkent is the tram. The joint-stock company "Tashkent tram" of Belgium has built a horse-drawn tram line from the railway station to the Chorsu market for 5 years. On March 30, 1901, the first line was opened. On November 5,

1947, trams began to run on electric power. Old people still remember the first conches. Until the 1940s, such trams were the only public means of transport in the city. Since 1926, 7 buses of the "Bents-Gaggenau" company, designed for 40 people, began to transport passengers in Tashkent [4]. After the war, multi-seater ZIS-154 buses were brought to Tashkent and other cities of our republic, and they were the first steps in bus passenger transportation. After that, the use of bus services in cities began to increase.

In 1947, the first trolleybus route was launched in Tashkent on the route from the railway station to Eski Jova.

As the city expanded and the number of its inhabitants increased, the number of tram lines, trolleybus and bus routes also increased. However, as a result of the growth of passenger traffic in the city, the search for new ways to solve problems began, and on this basis, the idea of building a metro line was born.

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